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CONSENT

I agree

That the University shall be entitled to use any results, materials or other outcomes arising from my project work for the purposes of non-commercial teaching and research, including collaboration.

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Student Signature: Olaoluwa Ogunyemi	Date Signed: 20/04/2023
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DEDICATION

I express my gratitude to God for guiding me and lighting up my path to success, and for never leaving me nor forsaking me.

I dedicate this work to my wife Titilayo and son Oreoluwa, who have always loved, supported and believed in me. This achievement is not only a fulfilment of my dream, but also a way to express my gratitude and love to you.

I hope Oreoluwa would find inspiration and encouragement in this work for his future endeavors.

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ABSTRACT

Small businesses in Nigeria play a vital role in the economy, but they often neglect the need to maintain a healthy cybersecurity posture despite the modern adoption of technology. They also face inadequate oversight from regulators and lack of awareness, skills, resources, and policies to protect their data and systems from cyberattacks. Moreover, they are smaller in scale and capacity compared to categories in more advanced economies where there is more literature on the cybersecurity practice by small businesses.

This research aims to bridge the gap of lack of research on the topic in Nigeria and to explore the challenges and best practices for designing and implementing a cybersecurity strategy for small businesses. The research will use a qualitative approach, conducting semi-structured interviews with small business owners, and employees. The research will also review the NDPR data protection requirements and identify the target level of compliance.

The research will also assess the strengths of different cybersecurity frameworks taking into account NDPR requirements and create a hybrid framework that fits the context of small businesses in Nigeria. The expected outcomes of the research are to provide a comprehensive overview of the cybersecurity situation of small businesses in Nigeria, to identify the main gaps and challenges they face, and to offer practical and feasible recommendations for enhancing their cybersecurity awareness, capabilities, and resilience.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) have been identified as key players in the growth and development of economies around the world. This is evident in their significant contribution to the individual nation's wealth. For instance, in Nigeria, micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) contributed 46.31% to the country's GDP in 2021 and accounted for 96% of businesses in the country (National Bureau of Statistics 2021).

SMEs are increasingly relying on technology to improve their business processes by leveraging it to collect, communicate, process and store data as a key element to their going concern. However, the increased reliance on technology has exposed them to a wide range of cyber threats, making them soft targets for cybercriminals and hackers because they lack resources to invest in information security like the big corporations (National Institute of Standards and Technology 2016). To address these concerns, the Nigerian government, in line with global best practices developed the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) to provide a data protection mandate for all organisations involved in processing and custodianship of data.

The motivation behind this dissertation topic is the increasing threats to information assets of small businesses in Nigeria and the growing need for small businesses to formulate cybersecurity strategies to protect data and comply with NDPR requirements. However, small businesses are faced with difficulty of navigating the various cybersecurity frameworks available to develop a suitable cybersecurity strategy unique to their business needs. Therefore, this research aims to address the gap by providing small businesses with alternative hybrid cybersecurity framework to effectively protect data and comply to NDPR requirements.

1.2 Research Aim

The aim of this dissertation is to develop a comprehensive hybrid cybersecurity framework that can help small businesses in Nigeria protect their data, information systems and comply with requirements of the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR). The research will contribute to a more secure digital environment and the body of knowledge for cybersecurity for small businesses.

1.3 Research Objectives

The project objectives are to evaluate the NDPR requirements and identify a target maturity level for small businesses to protect data and comply with the regulation. The current data protection strategies of small businesses in Nigeria will be assessed, a review will be performed on existing cybersecurity framework options for small businesses (i.e., NCSC Cybersecurity Small Business Guide, NCSC Cyber Essentials and NIST Small Business Information Security) to identify gaps in addressing NDPR data protection requirement. Consequently, an alternative hybrid cybersecurity framework control guidelines will be developed and implemented to improve data protection and enhance the security posture of small businesses. Lastly, I will obtain feedback from research subjects to evaluate impact of the recommendation and hybrid framework upon commencement of implementation.

1.4 Research Questions

This dissertation aims to explore the most common cybersecurity threats faced by small businesses in Nigeria, assess the current cybersecurity practices and identify the most effective cybersecurity strategies that can be implemented to mitigate these threats. The following research questions will guide this study:

- 1) What are the existing practises by small businesses in Nigeria to protect data and information assets?
- 2) What are the limitations to the existing data protection and information security practices by small businesses in Nigeria?
- 3) What are the existing frameworks available for small businesses in Nigeria to protect data and information assets in line with NDPR requirements?
- 4) What are the existing challenges to adoption and implementation of cyber security frameworks for small businesses in Nigeria?

1.5 Project Outline

This section will provide an overview of the project and outline the different chapters that will be discussed, such as:

Introduction:

This chapter provides an overview of the research topic, the motivation and rationale for the study, research aims and objectives, research questions, and scope of the study.

Literature Review:

This chapter provides a broad assessment of existing literature to identify the level of study regarding the cybersecurity strategy for data protection by small businesses in Nigeria. The literature review will cover topics such as threats to data security, NDPR objective, challenges to implementing cybersecurity program by SMEs, cyber risk management and cybersecurity framework options available for adoption by small businesses.

Project Specification:

This chapter outlines the specific project objectives highlighting steps to achieve the objectives, project methodology used to specify data collection methods and data analysis techniques to be used, and consideration for Legal, Ethical, Social and Professional issues. It also describes the research design and methodology in detail, including any limitations or challenges encountered during the research process.

Design and Implementation:

This chapter outlines the process for designing and implementing a hybrid cybersecurity framework as a strategy to boost cybersecurity posture and protect data in fulfillment of the NDPR requirements for small businesses in Nigeria. It will go into details about weighing the benefits and drawbacks of various existing cybersecurity frameworks for small businesses (i.e., NCSC Cybersecurity Small Business Guide, NCSC Cyber Essentials and NIST Small Business Information Security) and compare the findings to the NDPR's requirements for data protection, and the use the results to justify the creation of a hybrid cybersecurity framework.

Findings:

The Findings chapter will present result of gap analysis of compliance for the small businesses using case study to identify gaps in cybersecurity practices for small businesses in Nigeria with aim of answering research questions and set the ground for recommendations to address gaps.

Conclusions:

This chapter presents result of evaluation of feedback from research subjects on the effectiveness and impact of hybrid framework being implemented. Next, it summarises the key findings of the research, including any limitations or challenges encountered during the study. It also provides recommendations for small businesses in Nigeria on how to improve their cyber security strategy and protect data in compliance with GDPR requirements. Finally, it offers suggestions for future research in this field.

1.6 Conclusion

The findings of this research will provide valuable insights into the cybersecurity challenges faced by small businesses in meeting data protection requirement of the GDPR and inform the development of cybersecurity strategies to address challenges. Lastly, this study aims to contribute to the development of a more secure and resilient cybersecurity strategy for small businesses in Nigeria by ensuring they are better positioned to protect their data and help defend against cyber threats.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter analyses relevant literature with aims to investigate the cybersecurity and data protection practices of small businesses in Nigeria. The objective is to assess the adequacy of the current strategy or frameworks being adopted and to evaluate the existing data protection practices of small businesses.

First, this chapter will examine threats to data security and current statistics. Then, a literature review will be conducted to review the requirements of the Nigeria data protection regulations (NDPR) and appraise its objectives, Consequently, the review will also identify challenges faced by small businesses in implementing cybersecurity programs that will ensure data protection in accordance with the NDPR mandate.

Next, the chapter will assess the cyber risk management approach and practices of small businesses, as well as the existing information security strategies, then appraise the cybersecurity frameworks available and being adopted by them. Lastly, I will summarise review of related literature.

2.2 Selection Strategy

A survey of existing literature was performed to evaluate past studies on cybersecurity practices and strategies by small businesses in developing countries. PRISMA methodology (Page et al. 2021) was used to search for relevant papers and I performed literature search using RGU online library which indexes and searches popular academic and research databases and registers such as Web of Science, Scopus, IEEE Xplore, Science Direct, and Taylor & Francis online. In addition, Google scholar was used to widen search to perform citation and related article search. Furthermore, a review of referenced journal articles was also performed to widen search.

Search word and phrases used contains the following terms: ("cybersecurity") OR ("cybersecurity framework") OR ("cybersecurity strategy") OR ("data protection") OR ("data privacy") OR ("data security") OR ("information security")) AND (((("SME*") OR ("small business*") OR ("medium scale") OR ("small scale*")) AND (("Nigeria") OR ("Africa") OR ("Developing countr*")))). Search and selection strategy was limited to only literatures written in English for the analysis.

Due to the introduction of the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) in 2019, the search date range was filtered to only return results from 2017 to the present. This was done to ensure that recent and relevant literatures are analysed to evaluate current data protection strategy and practices by small businesses in Nigeria.

Figure 2.1 Prisma Methodology

Figure 2.1 outlines paper selection strategy, a total of 49 journal articles were sourced in the identification phase, during screening i excluded 11 records due to duplication of content, non-availability to public, fee-dependent access limitation, etc. Further review revealed insufficient analysis in 17 articles thereby retaining 21 articles for review.

2.3 Threats to data security for small businesses

The adoption and continued use of information technology systems in business operations by small and medium sized enterprises in developing countries has the potential to bring significant benefits and at the same time could expose them to cyber threat (Kabanda, Tanner and Kent 2018). This is particularly true for small businesses in Nigeria that are increasingly leveraging technology (including cloud) in their operations. According to De Crescenzo (cited in Perez 2020) the adoption of cloud services presents a new challenge for small businesses that do not have the relevant resources and programs to train their employees on safe and secure internet browsing practices.

44USC (cited in National Institute of Standards and Technology 2016 p.2) defined information security as “The protection of information and information systems from unauthorized access, use, disclosure, disruption, modification, or destruction in order to provide confidentiality, integrity, and availability”. Confidentiality, integrity, and availability are the three pillars of data security, Confidentiality is when your data is protected from unauthorised access while Integrity involves making sure data is unaltered in its content and details and Availability is making data available to business and customers as at when needed. Threat to data security involves any activity that poses a compromise to either or combination of confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data.

Verizon (2022) in the Data Breach Investigation Report 2022 depicted in Figure 2.2 identified the six most common data breach threat facing small businesses to include:

- Ransomware: it is a type of malware deployed by cybercriminals which prevents data access to authorized users usually by encrypting the files. The cybercriminal will demand a ransom in exchange for decryption key. According to Verizon (2022) ransomware is the number one threat to data security in the survey and there has been an upward trend with almost 13% increase in ransomware.
- Use of stolen credentials: this occurs when a malicious attacker uses different means to steal credentials to gain unauthorized access to user account and system.
- Phishing: this is a form of social engineering when an attacker tricks users to reveal sensitive information, click malicious link or download malicious files on their information system.
- Pretexting: is a made-up scheme developed by threat actors for the purpose of stealing a victim’s sensitive and confidential data.
- Trojan: are programs that appear legitimate to perform one task but in reality, is performing different malicious tasks on information system.
- Exploit vulnerabilities: this includes or involves any other vulnerability in system or process that could compromise information asset and lead to breach of data.

Figure 2.2 Report of Data Breach for Small Businesses

Small businesses need to fortify their defenses to protect data and prevent data breach. According to World Economic Forum (2023) attackers’ advantage is they only need to find one exploitable weakness and concentrates efforts towards penetration using different techniques. Successful data

breaches are costly to business operations and going concern, this agrees with Perez (2020) who argued, security breaches lead to loss of sensitive information which could have both professional and personal cost tied to them and ultimately result in financial loss to the business in responding to the breach by purchasing tools and services to recover lost or stolen data.

2.4 Nigeria Data Protection Regulation Objective

The rapid digitisation of business operations has presented small businesses with numerous benefits, such as improved connectivity and competitive advantage, but also presents new challenges such as more exposure to cyber-attacks (Emer, Unterhofer and Rauch 2021). To combat this, governments around the world have reformed or developed data protection regulations to ensure that businesses implement relevant security measures to protect their data from abuse and malicious usage. The Nigerian government, for instance, introduced the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) in 2019 to protect the rights of data subjects and mandate data processors and custodians to implement data security measures. From inception, the National Information Technology Development Authority (NITDA) was tasked with enforcing compliance of NDPR, but the function was transferred to Nigeria Data Protection Bureau (NDPB) upon creation of the bureau in February 2022 as a key drive to the National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS) of the Nigeria Government (Amadi 2022).

Small businesses use data to improve productivity, facilitate innovation, and make informed decisions (Rawindaran et al. 2021). The NDPR defines boundaries for objective usage of data, sets data security requirements for businesses and mandates them to implement framework and adopt relevant technologies to protect against data breach (National Information Technology Development Agency 2020). Implementation of the NDPR requirements ensures businesses adopt and implement cybersecurity frameworks to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of their information assets. As highlighted by the World Economic Forum (2023), privacy regulations are effective in reducing cyber risk for organisations. Rawindaran et al. (2021) also support the effectiveness of guidelines and policies in protecting data as it will propel businesses to make informed decision and operate in a safe and secure way to protect the data they manage.

Regulations define enforceable responsibilities for businesses towards achieving the objective of the regulation. The NDPR helped define and protect the rights of data subjects and specified the data security requirements for data processors and controllers in Nigeria.

2.5 Challenges to implementing cybersecurity strategy by small businesses

Cybersecurity is often practiced on adhoc basis by small and medium sized enterprises, it is uncommon to see small businesses proactively budget for and invest in cybersecurity program. If not compelled by regulators, standard setters (e.g., PCIDSS), or critical business partners there is usually no motivation to implement and maintain a structured cybersecurity program. Small and medium sized enterprises work with false assumption that their value is insignificant for attackers. Hence, this is not properly assessed when conducting risk assessments to aid decision making on developing and maintaining cybersecurity programs (Perez 2020).

Despite continued adoption and leverage of technology – including cloud technology by SMEs in their business operations, investment in security tools and technology is inadequate to protect information assets. Berry & Berry (cited in Perez 2020) found that small businesses often need to balance the cost of integrating internet-based technology and systems with the cost of securing them. Perez (2020)

also mentioned small businesses do not consider cybersecurity cost as essential; it is often treated as discretionary spending with small budgetary allocation and lack of advanced security tools.

Emer, Unterhofer and Rauch (2021) highlighted major difference between large businesses and small businesses in adoption of cybersecurity framework to protect their assets as limited monetary resources and investment in cybersecurity and lack of technical knowhow on implementing and maintaining a structured cybersecurity framework. This poses threat to small business and medium sized enterprises and makes them soft target for attackers. Furthermore, a technically skilled and security minded personnel is critical to implementation and maintenance of a cybersecurity program for businesses, small businesses often lack the financial resources to recruit, train and maintain technically proficient full-time employees dedicated to security of information assets and combating cyber threats (Perez 2020).

Failure to implement a cybersecurity program exposes the business and the cost of cyber-breach is high in terms of financial and reputation damage, it cost less to be proactive in preventing threats than responding and recovering from attacks.

2.6 Cyber risk management

Small businesses just like the large organisation counterpart faces cyber threats that could be detrimental to their operations and going concern, hence, they need to adopt a structured approach to assessing threats, putting in place measures to proactively prevent threats and developing response plan to address. According to Hoppe, Gatzert and Gruner (2021), small businesses need to be more proficient in managing cyber risks emanating from adoption of technology as a tool adopted for business operation.

Steps for implementing security strategy involves identifying the root cause of vulnerabilities, developing policies, and implementing strategy to mitigate risks (Perez 2020). As Cunningham & Head (cited in Perez 2020 p.15) noted "cybersecurity has shifted from best practice to an essential business driver as market reliance on information technology increase." Fortunately, there are free industry standards and frameworks, such as National Cyber Security Centre's Small Business Guide, Cyber Essentials, and the NIST Small Business Information Security. These frameworks provide guidelines and best practices for small businesses to improve their cybersecurity posture.

In conclusion, cyber attackers are becoming increasingly sophisticated and are now more likely to focus on business disruption and reputational damage (World Economic Forum 2023). A good strategy for small businesses is implementation of information security and cybersecurity management to improve the security controls (Antunes et al. 2021). This will ensure protection of information assets and ultimately reduce their risk of being victimised by cyber cybercriminals.

2.7 Cybersecurity framework or strategy

There are several cybersecurity frameworks available to develop robust cybersecurity strategy to protect data for businesses. Owing to the challenges of lack of resources and limited technical capabilities for most SMEs, relevant governmental bodies and private standard setters have developed frameworks which provides practical guidelines and best practices recommendations for SMEs to build resilient cybersecurity strategy. Protection against threat and attacks is crucial with the advancement of digital transformation for businesses (Emer, Unterhofer and Rauch 2021). This section showcases some of the cybersecurity framework options available for small businesses to adopt and

implement to build a robust cybersecurity posture capable of protecting their information assets. Lastly, an assessment of merit and draw backs of the frameworks will be performed on capability of the framework to address the NDPR requirements.

2.7.1 National Cyber Security Center Cybersecurity: Small Business Guide

In response to identified cyber threats and challenges facing small business in developing cybersecurity strategy to prevent or respond to the threats National Cyber Security Centre (2017) developed Cyber Security: Small Business Guide to provide low cost and easy to use guide for small businesses to develop and maintain cybersecurity program.

The guide covers 5 topics including:

1. backing up data: this specifies things businesses must consider in developing data backup for the business's going concern to aid recovery in the event of disruption.
2. Protection against malware: it spells out different strategies to protect against malware infestation within businesses.
3. Keeping your smart phone and tablets safe: mobile devices play a role in everyday use and activities by business owners and employees and could be open attack surface if not protected. The guide spells out tips to help secure mobile devices and the information on them.
4. Using password to protect your data: this specifies best practices in developing and using a healthy password management strategy to secure data and devices storing them.
5. Avoid phishing attack: this specifies physical and technical strategies to identify, prevent and report attacks.

The small business guide is accompanied with an actions document which contains best practices guide for business to improve their cybersecurity. It has a checklist under the following headers.

- Policy actions.
- Technical actions.
- Training and awareness actions.

2.7.2 National Cyber Security Center: Cyber Essentials

NCSC Cyber Essentials is an assurance framework that provides technical control requirements to protect businesses from cyber threats. The framework spells technical control themes to provide guidelines on development of security measures to cover both on-prem and cloud devices and software.

Per National Cyber Security Centre (2022) in document titled “Cyber Essentials Requirements for IT infrastructure”, the Cyber Essentials requirements are categorized under 5 technical control themes to ensure protection of information assets:

1. Firewall: it provides recommendation on how to ensure proper configuration and application of firewall rules to monitor and filter access for both incoming and outgoing communications are applied to information systems and resources.
2. Secure configuration: it provides guideline on how to configure network devices to reduce inherent vulnerabilities in systems.
3. User access control: it specifies requirements to ensure proper definition and assignment of access and that access are granted to authorised users on need basis to perform their role.
4. Malware protection control requirements: this lists steps to prevent malware from infecting systems, including installing and configuring anti-malwares software to protect system from malwares, prevent connection to malicious websites, etc.

5. Security update management: it provides requirements and guidelines to ensure devices and software are not exposed to known security flaws for which fixes are available.

Figure 2.3 highlights the scope of IT infrastructure being covered in the NCSC cyber essentials for certification purposes.

Figure 2.3 Scope of the requirements for IT infrastructure

Small businesses can also apply for Cybersecurity Essentials certification, and there are free self-assessment questions towards certification that organisations can leverage to perform self-assessment based on the framework's technical control requirements.

2.7.3 NIST Cybersecurity Framework and NIST Small Business Information Security

NIST Cyber security framework provides a set of best practices and guidelines to assess and manage cyber risk for businesses. The framework adopts a risk-based approach to managing cybersecurity risk and is divided into three parts: the Framework Core, the Framework Implementation Tiers, and the Framework Profiles (National Institute of Standards and Technology 2018).

According to National Institute of Standards and Technology (2018), the Framework core is categorised into 5 functions which are subdivided into 23 categories and further categorised into 108 subcategories. Figure 2.4 shows diagram of the framework's core functions and categories.

The framework core functions are:

- Identify: build organizational awareness of how to manage cybersecurity risk to systems, people, assets, data, and capabilities.
- Protect: establish and implement appropriate security measures to protect information assets and ensure delivery of critical services.
- Detect: develop and implement appropriate activities to detect the occurrence of a cybersecurity event.

- Respond: develop and implement appropriate activities to deal with detected cybersecurity incident.
- Recover: develop and implement appropriate plans and processes to maintain resilience and to recover any capabilities or services that were impaired due to a cybersecurity incident.

Function Unique Identifier	Function	Category Unique Identifier	Category
ID	Identify	ID.AM	Asset Management
		ID.BE	Business Environment
		ID.GV	Governance
		ID.RA	Risk Assessment
		ID.RM	Risk Management Strategy
		ID.SC	Supply Chain Risk Management
PR	Protect	PR.AC	Identity Management and Access Control
		PR.AT	Awareness and Training
		PR.DS	Data Security
		PR.IP	Information Protection Processes and Procedures
		PR.MA	Maintenance
		PR.PT	Protective Technology
DE	Detect	DE.AE	Anomalies and Events
		DE.CM	Security Continuous Monitoring
		DE.DP	Detection Processes
RS	Respond	RS.RP	Response Planning
		RS.CO	Communications
		RS.AN	Analysis
		RS.MI	Mitigation
		RS.IM	Improvements
RC	Recover	RC.RP	Recovery Planning
		RC.IM	Improvements
		RC.CO	Communications

Figure 2.4 NIST cybersecurity framework function and category

Rawindaran et al. (2021) argued that NIST cybersecurity framework guidelines for cyber risk management requires skilled and competent staff to manage the process and technology, a resource that small enterprises frequently lack access to due to capacity and resource constraints. NIST in response to these constraints published small business information security: the fundamentals as a non-technical and easy to use reference guideline for small business to develop and maintain cybersecurity program. It was designed as a quick start guide based on the NIST cybersecurity framework to help small businesses implement cybersecurity activities (National Institute of Standards and Technology 2016).

2.7.4 Assessment of cybersecurity frameworks

NCSC Small Business Guide, Cyber Essentials, and NIST Small Business Information Security are all designed to help small businesses improve their cybersecurity posture. Table 2.1 highlights the merits and demerits of the respective frameworks based on my assessment.

S/n	Cybersecurity Framework	Merit	Demerit
1	NIST Small Business Information Security	Comprehensive coverage with a more holistic approach, including identification, protection, detection, response, and recovery.	Complex and requires significant investment of time and resources.
		Widely trusted, tested, and accepted framework.	No external certification available.
			Ease of customization can lead to inconsistent implementation and a lack of external validation.
2	NCSC Cybersecurity Small Business Guide	Easy to understand and implement for non-technical personnel.	The framework is not certifiable.
		Comprehensive coverage of cybersecurity themes including data backup, device security, malware prevention, and password protection.	Lack of governance and risk management coverage.
		Cost-effective and easy to implement.	Limited guidance on continuous improvement and external validation.
		The guide is more flexible and adaptable than other frameworks.	
3	NCSC Cyber Essentials	Provides a comprehensive and easy-to-follow guide for implementing cybersecurity controls.	Only technical controls are covered.
		Covers all IT infrastructure assets, including cloud services and mobile devices.	Limited coverage of governance and risk management and data protection awareness training.
		Certification is possible, which can boost stakeholder confidence.	Limited guidance on continuous improvement and external validation.
		Cost-effective certification in comparison to other frameworks such as ISO 27001, PCIDSS.	

Table 2. 1 Merit and demerit of different cybersecurity framework options for small businesses

In summary, each framework has its own set of merits and demerits, and businesses can select the one that matches their needs and resources. The NCSC Small Business Guide and Cyber Essentials are

simpler and cheaper options, while the NIST Small Business Information Security is more thorough but demands more time and resources.

2.8 Related work

In research conducted in South Africa, Kabanda, Tanner, and Kent (2018) identified internal and external factors that influence SMEs' perception of cybersecurity and constrain cybersecurity implementation. These factors include limited budget priority, lack of management support, and a perception that they are not likely targets for cybercrime. The study highlights the need for greater awareness and understanding of cybersecurity risks among SMEs, as well as the importance of regulatory pressure to encourage adoption of cybersecurity measures.

Tam, Rao, and Hall (2021) identified a range of challenges that SMEs in Australia face in implementing cybersecurity measures, such as technical challenges, human resource constraints, and organizational/process maturity issues. The study emphasizes the need for SMEs to consider outsourcing information systems management to third-party vendors to overcome these challenges. This supports Perez (2020) assertion that SMEs in the US often struggle to implement comprehensive security plans due to financial and resource burdens. Outsourcing information systems management to third-party vendors, such as cloud providers, can be an effective solution to address these limitations.

Barosy (2019) provided operational strategies for protecting businesses from cyber-attacks, emphasizing the importance of effective leadership, cybersecurity awareness, and reliance on third-party vendors. These strategies can help SMEs overcome resource constraints and develop more comprehensive security plans. Eilts (2020) suggests that cybersecurity guidance, such as the NIST cybersecurity framework, can help SMEs improve their cybersecurity posture by providing a structured approach to cybersecurity preparedness. Although cybersecurity frameworks are good strategy to develop structured and robust cybersecurity posture, there is need to consider size, scale, and resource capacity for small businesses. Antunes et al. (2021) found that implementing the ISO 27001 standard could be challenging for SMEs due to their variance in size, human resources, and IT levels. This suggests that SMEs require tailored approaches that consider their unique characteristics.

To further elaborate on the literature review, the studies collectively highlight the challenges faced by small and medium-sized enterprises in implementing effective cybersecurity measures. The findings suggest that SMEs have limited resources and expertise, which can hinder their ability to adequately protect themselves from cyber threats.

2.9 Conclusion

The literature review highlights the need for tailored approaches to help SMEs overcome the unique challenges they face in implementing effective cybersecurity measures. By adopting a more proactive approach to cybersecurity, SMEs can better protect themselves from cyber-threats and minimize the impact of cyber-attacks. However, there is a paucity of research on their cybersecurity practices and strategies to protect data and comply with the NDPR data protection regulations in the era of data-driven business models.

Moreover, the existing literatures are also constrained by different definition of small businesses highlighted in Figure 2.5 with notable difference in scale and capacity thereby limiting the applicability of literature from other contexts to the Nigerian context.

Country or Institution	Micro		Small		Medium		Citation
	Turnover	Employee	Turnover	Employee	Turnover	Employee	
UK	≤ € 2 million	n < 10	≤ € 10 million	n < 50	≤ € 50 million	< 250	Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office 2022
European Union	≤ € 2 million	n < 10	≤ € 10 million	n < 50	≤ € 50 million	< 250	European Commission n.d.
Nigeria	≤ ₦ 5 million	n < 10	≤ ₦ 50 million	n < 100	≤ ₦ 500 million	< 300	Bank of Industry n.d.
World Bank	< \$100,000	n < 10	< \$100,000 - < \$ 3 million	10 - 49	\$ 3 million - \$ 15 million	50 - 300	International Finance Corporation n.d.

Figure 2.5 Different definitions of micro, small and medium sized enterprise

Therefore, this research aims to provide contextual insights and contribute to the growing literature on cybersecurity strategy for small businesses.

3.0 PROJECT SPECIFICATION

3.1 Project Objective

The objective of this project is to evaluate the cybersecurity strategies implemented by small businesses in Nigeria to protect data and comply with the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR). The NDPR regulation is aimed at safeguarding personal data and ensuring privacy rights of data subjects (National Information Technology Development Agency 2020).

This research study focused on the following four objectives to achieve the main goal:

- 1) Evaluate the requirements of data protection regulation (i.e., NDPR) requirements to identify a target maturity level required by small businesses to meet regulatory requirements. The following steps will be taken to achieve this objective:
 - Examine the NDPR to identify data protection requirements.
 - Determine the desired level of maturity that small businesses must attain to satisfy regulatory obligations.
- 2) Assess the current maturity level and get familiar with data protection strategies, implementation, and practices by small businesses in Nigeria. To achieve this objective, i will conduct interviews with small businesses and review existing practices to learn more about current data protection strategy and to identify areas needing improvement.
- 3) Assess the alternative cybersecurity framework control guidelines against NDPR requirement target maturity. This will be achieved through review of NIST Cybersecurity Framework, NCSC Small Business Guide and Cyber Essentials with the aim of developing a hybrid framework to address the NDPR data protection requirements.
- 4) Propose and implement recommendations to improve security posture and enhance data protection in line with regulatory requirements. To achieve this objective, i will provide and implement recommendations to address the gaps identified in project objective 2 using the hybrid framework developed in project objective 3.

3.2 Project Methodology

3.2.1 Introduction

The purpose of this dissertation is to analyse cybersecurity strategies for small businesses in Nigeria to protect data in line with NDPR requirements. To achieve this, a qualitative research methodology will be employed.

3.2.2 Research design

Case study methodology will be used for the research design, this will enable thorough analysis of cybersecurity posture of research subjects to assess cybersecurity posture and identify existing practices by small businesses in Nigeria.

3.2.3 Data collection

Qualitative data collection method will be used to gather data from research subjects, it will include interviews conducted with the small business owners, the dedicated personnel for the respective

businesses, walkthrough to review system configurations for implemented security tools and questionnaire developed using the hybrid framework (Appendix D) to assess security measures put in place to cater for data protection requirements of NDPR.

3.2.4 Data analysis

Qualitative data analysis will be performed to identify patterns and common themes in the data. The analysis will be used to identify data protection strategies used by small businesses in Nigeria. Data analysis within this study will be divided into two stages:

Stage 1: "gap assessment" by reviewing existing cybersecurity strategies and implemented framework by small businesses using requirements in the developed hybrid cybersecurity framework for evaluation.

Stage 2: "provision of recommendation and implementation of alternative framework – using requirements of the hybrid cybersecurity framework" as a cybersecurity strategy for small businesses to ensure protection of data in line with NDPR requirements.

3.2.5 Functional requirements

In answering the research questions, the aim of this research is to find a suitable framework that will adequately provide cybersecurity protection for small businesses and ensure they comply with NDPR data protection requirement.

To answer the research question and proffer a solution, Table 3.1 presents the functional requirements for the framework using four levels of priority: Must have, Should have, Could have, and Won't have. These levels indicate how essential or desirable each requirement is for the framework to achieve its objective (Korolov 2023).

S/n	MoSCoW	Description	Requirements
1	Must-have	These are the essential requirements that the hybrid framework must have to achieve the main objective of the dissertation question	Applying a SWOT method to evaluate existing cybersecurity framework (i.e., NCSC Cybersecurity Small Business Guide, NCSC Cyber Essentials, and NIST Small Business Information Security) to find out the strengths and weaknesses of each framework in relation to meeting the data protection requirement of the NDPR.
			Development of hybrid cybersecurity framework by combining best practices and standards from all 3 cybersecurity frameworks under evaluation
			Evaluate the gaps in the existing cybersecurity strategy using the developed hybrid framework, by comparing the current cybersecurity practice of small businesses in Nigeria with the requirements in hybrid cybersecurity framework as the standard.
			Propose recommendation using requirements from the hybrid cybersecurity framework to address identified gaps.

			<p>Hybrid cybersecurity framework requirements should be capable of addressing the cybersecurity needs and challenges of small businesses in Nigeria who collect, store or process data.</p> <p>Design detailed specification of the hybrid cybersecurity framework in clear and easy term for use by small businesses</p> <p>Hybrid framework will be arranged in a thematic style to correspond to the core functions of NIST cybersecurity framework: Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond and Recover to ensure integrated approach is adopted.</p>
2	Should-have	These are the desirable requirements that the hybrid framework should have in order to enhance the quality and validity of the dissertation question.	<p>Perform full implementation of recommendations for small businesses involved in study.</p> <p>Evaluate the ease and impact of hybrid framework implementation by getting feedback from research subjects.</p> <p>Recommended security tools, templates and policies will be sourced from free and open source.</p> <p>Assessment of potential risks and mitigation strategies associated with the development and implementation of the hybrid framework</p>
3	Could-have	These are the optional requirements that the hybrid framework could have in order to provide additional value and insight for the dissertation question.	<p>Perform a benchmark review of the hybrid framework with ISO 27001 to assess the alignment, gaps, and improvement areas of the hybrid framework with the international standard for information security management.</p> <p>Comprehensive implementation or deployment plan for the hybrid framework</p> <p>Design hybrid framework specification beyond the scope of the research</p> <p>Evaluation or monitoring plan beyond the timeframe of the research</p>
4	Won't-have	These are the out-of-scope requirements that the hybrid framework won't have in order to limit the scope and complexity of the dissertation question.	<p>Hybrid framework will not have any requirement outside of those specified in the 3 frameworks being merged</p> <p>Use of a cost-benefit analysis tool or technique to estimate and compare the costs and benefits of adopting the hybrid framework</p> <p>Perform post-implementation review of the hybrid framework to measure its feasibility, effectiveness, and efficiency in meeting cybersecurity objectives of small businesses and complying with the data protection mandate of the NDPR.</p> <p>Certification of the hybrid framework by any certification body</p>

Table 3. 1 Functional requirements for hybrid cybersecurity framework

For this research, I will not be categorising requirements as either functional or non-functional requirements due to the nature of the research which is not creation of web application.

3.3 Legal, Ethical, Social and Professional Issues

3.3.1 Introduction

The key focus of the research is the development and implementation of hybrid cybersecurity framework for small businesses in Nigeria as a cybersecurity strategy to safeguard data and comply with NDPR requirements. There is a need to maintain confidentiality and privacy of research subject and conduct study in a credible and reliable way, hence, there is need to consider legal, ethical, social and professional issues and address to ensure the research is conducted responsibly whilst complying with legal and ethical requirements.

3.3.2 Legal issues

One of the legal considerations to consider in this dissertation is the Nigeria Data Protection Regulations (NDPR), which mandates that personal data must be treated in a way that guarantees the protection and confidentiality of the data (National Information Technology Development Agency 2020). It is crucial to preserve research subjects' privacy and make sure that their personal information is protected in accordance with the NDPR mandate. During the research, I reviewed internal policies, processes, technology, and cybersecurity strategy of the research subjects. Utmost secrecy and codification of business name was employed to ensure anonymity.

In performance of the study and assessment, the following steps were taken to prevent abuse of data and ensure anonymity of data subject:

- I had a formal kick-off meeting with all research subjects to agree on terms and conditions of involvement and signed a non-disclosure agreement with them in advance.
- All documents and data to be assessed were hosted on online drive created and managed by research subjects, with access granted to me as the researcher using my school email and research subjects employed 2FA where possible.
- All reviews were performed on the online drive without downloading any document to work or review offline.
- I did not cite or quote identifiable information about subject in the research documentation.

Throughout the research, this legal requirement was followed, to prevent any legal repercussions for research subjects and researcher.

3.3.3 Ethical issues

The confidentiality and privacy of research subjects are relevant concerns addressed in this research. The following steps were taken to safeguard research subjects' personal information:

- A non-disclosure agreement (NDA) was signed before accessing any confidential data from the research subjects.

- The terms and conditions of the NDA were adhered to strictly and no identifiable information about the research subjects' businesses or personnel was revealed in any form.
- Except for information security policies, a comprehensive questionnaire and interviews with business owners and designated personnel were used for assessment instead of reviewing other confidential documents including policies and SOPs for assessment.
- Confidential information was not shared through unsecure or private channels.

Lastly, as a professional courtesy and a value-added service, I committed to working with the participating small businesses to ensure full implementation of the recommendation and framework upon conclusion of research despite the short timeframe.

3.3.4 Social issues

Social issues considered are related to the potential negative impact to research subjects that could result from a breach of confidentiality. The research subjects are small businesses, and any breach could have significant social consequences including reputational damage, loss of revenue, identity theft and legal repercussions. The following steps were taken to address the social issues:

- Ensured strict compliance to the terms and conditions of the NDA by upholding research subjects' privacy to avoid any harm from a data breach.
- Ensured secrecy and anonymity of research subjects to protect their reputations and main stakeholders' trust.
- Adhered to ethical principles and professional standards during the study.

3.3.5 Professional issues

Professional issues refer to the standards of conduct, behavior, and values expected of individuals or organizations in a particular profession. In the context of this research, professional issues revolve around the ethical and moral responsibilities in conducting a cybersecurity study for small businesses in Nigeria. Some of the professional issues considered during the research include:

- a) **Competency:** necessary skills, knowledge, and expertise to undertake the study requires possession of a deep understanding of cybersecurity, data protection regulations, and small business operations. I have the requisite skills through training, professional qualifications (certified in ISO 27001 Lead Auditor, CISA, CRISC and CISM), experience in both internal and external auditor performing cybersecurity strategy review, and knowledgeable on data protection regulation and small business operation audit using relevant frameworks to provide recommendation and solutions that would contribute to the body of knowledge. In addition, I am committed to continuous professional development which is in line with the BCS principle of competence and integrity.
- b) **Impartiality:** As a researcher, it is essential to maintain impartiality and avoid conflicts of interest. To address the issue of impartiality, I ensured all analysis is based on verifiable facts and data, and not influenced by personal or external factors. I will also disclose any conflicts of interest and take appropriate measures to mitigate any potential bias or prejudice. This approach is consistent with the BCS principle of professionalism, which emphasizes the need for objectivity and impartiality in the course of work.

- c) Respect for privacy and confidentiality: I have professional obligation to respect the privacy and confidentiality of the research subjects by ensuring proper anonymization of sensitive and identifiable information and make use of secured and encrypted communication channel throughout the research, to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the data.

In conclusion, the British Computer Society (BCS) has a code of conduct that outlines the ethical and professional standards that its members should adhere to in the course of their work. The BCS code of conduct is based on four main principles: professionalism, respect, integrity, and competence (British Computer Society 2022). In the context of this research, the professional issues identified above are closely linked to the BCS code of conduct.

3.3.6 Conclusion

A leak of information or lack of anonymization would be in contravention to the terms of the signed non-disclosure agreement, the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) and would not satisfy the British Computer Society code of conduct. Hence, I have taken the necessary steps to identify and mitigate the legal, ethical, social, and professional issues to ensure quality of outcome without compromise or consequential loss from performing the research.

3.4 Project risks

This project faced some limitations and challenges that required mitigating strategies to ensure its success. Some of the limitations and mitigants are:

- Sampling: The recruitment of research subjects was done through social media, which could limit the diversity and representativeness of the sample. To mitigate this, a kick-off meeting was held with seven potential research subjects to explain the project plan, timeline, and expectations (Appendix C). After the meeting, four subjects agreed to participate in the project.
- Communication: The communication with the research subjects was dependent on their availability and preference of platform. This could cause delays or misunderstandings in the data collection process. To mitigate this, research subjects created their respective online drive location to share documents and data securely and efficiently. To prevent research subject fatigue, I flexed my schedules to meet their availability, most of which were on weekends.
- Data Protection: The project involved collecting and processing personal and confidential data from the research subjects, which could pose a risk of data breach or misuse. To mitigate this, a data protection strategy was developed and implemented to ensure compliance with NDPR regulations. The strategy included obtaining consent from management and business owners on participation, agreeing on mode of communication and signing a non-disclosure agreement (NDA) before accessing any confidential data, and anonymising documentation.

3.5 Conclusion

The result of this study will add to the existing body of knowledge on cybersecurity strategies for small businesses in Nigeria and will offer recommendations for strengthening cybersecurity posture of small businesses to ensure they put in adequate measures to protect data in line with NDPR requirements.

4.0 DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, I documented design and implementation of a hybrid cybersecurity framework as suitable cybersecurity strategy for small businesses in Nigeria, I started by reviewing merits and demerits of three different cybersecurity framework and provided justifications for hybrid cybersecurity framework whilst detailing the steps taken to develop the framework. Lastly, I presented steps involved in implementation.

4.2 Justification and design of hybrid cybersecurity framework

4.2.1 NDPR Requirements

NDPR mandated all businesses involved in controlling or processing data to perform periodic data protection audit. According to National Information Technology Development Agency (2020), a data protection audit is a systematic investigation of the records, processes, and procedures of data controllers and processors to ensure compliance with the requirements of the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) and their data protection policies.

To assist with data protection audit, NITDA developed an audit template for NDPR compliance. The audit template provides guidelines for businesses to develop and implement processes to ensure compliance with the NDPR requirements. The following are relevant highlights from National Information Technology Development Agency (2019) audit template considered in the assessment of the individual cybersecurity framework and eventual development of hybrid framework to fulfil the NDPR requirements:

- Implementation of information security standard (Article 2.6)
- Existence of documented data breach incident management procedure (Article 2.1(d))
- Existence of data protection compliance and review mechanism (Article 2.1)
- Develop capacity building plan for compliance with data protection for all members of staff and relevant third-party contractor (Article 2.6)
- Review and update of HR policy to ensure personal data of employees are handled in compliance with the NDPR (Article 4.1(5))
- Implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to show you have considered and integrated data protection into your processing activities (Article 2.5(d))
- Adaptation of pseudonymisation, anonymisation and encryption methods to reduce exposure of personal data (Article 2.6)
- Put in place adequate information systems security that complies with ISO 27001 covering physical, logical, technical, and operational measures that ensure the security of personal data being processed (Article 4.1(5)f)

The individual cybersecurity frameworks (i.e., NCSC Cybersecurity Small Business Guide, NCSC Cyber Essentials and NIST Small Business Information Security) that are available for small businesses to improve their cybersecurity practices have some limitations and gaps when it comes to complying with the data protection requirements of the NDPR as highlighted in Table 2.1. Therefore, it is necessary to combine and customize the frameworks in a way that can leverage their combined

strengths and address their weaknesses. This can help create a more robust cybersecurity posture for small businesses that can protect data in accordance with NDPR requirements.

4.2.2 Hybrid Cybersecurity Framework Design

The design of the hybrid cybersecurity framework involved a combination of the NIST Small Business Information Security, NCSC Cybersecurity Small Business Guide and NCSC Cyber Essentials. The hybrid framework will aim to address the limitations of each individual framework and provide a comprehensive and customized solution for small businesses to meet data protection requirements from NDPR. The framework has a total of 5 categories further broken down into 40 control requirements.

Control requirements in the framework were assigned priority ranking based on impact-urgency-priority matrix, the ranking is a way of determining which security control requirements of the framework are more urgent and important to implement (Mathenge 2020). The ranking is based on the evidence of the cybersecurity threats and the effectiveness of the security controls. The ranking has four levels:

- Highly critical: The security control requirement is essential to mitigate a threat scenario that is very likely and very harmful.
- Critical: The security control requirement is important to mitigate a threat scenario that is very likely or very harmful.
- Medium: The security control requirement is useful to mitigate a threat scenario that is moderately likely and moderately harmful.
- Low: The security control requirement is optional to mitigate a threat scenario that is unlikely or harmless.

S/n	Category	Ref ID	CSF Source	Requirements	Key Objective(s)	Criticality ranking
1	Identify	ID1	NIST	Create an information security policy.	It should serve as the overarching document detailing organisation's objective to maintain confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information assets.	Highly critical
		ID2	NIST	Employees must read and consent to information security policy requirements	To ensure employees understand policy objectives and acceptable practices as defined in the policy	Highly critical
		ID3	NIST	Maintain an inventory of all your critical assets with relevant specifications including asset name,	Enable businesses take proper stock, monitor critical assets, and implement asset protection strategies	Highly critical

				operating systems, versions etc.		
		ID4	NIST	Test employees understanding of information security policy objectives annually or whenever there is a major change to the policy	To reinforce knowledge and understanding of policy objectives and expectations from employees	Highly critical
		ID5	NIST	Create HR files for employees and update consents and evidence of test results on understanding of information security policies	To track progress in understanding and familiarisation of employees to business's information security policy objectives	Highly critical
		ID6	SBG	Have dedicated personnel(s) sign up for cyber threat alerts and newsletters	To monitor emerging threats and ensure proper planning and consideration in developing cybersecurity strategies (policy update, cyber awareness training resources etc.) to prevent cyber-attacks	Critical
		ID7	SBG	Perform frequent review of asset inventory	To ensure complete and accurate details are captured	Critical
2	Protect	PR1	SBG	Install antivirus on all relevant IT systems and devices (laptop, PC, smart devices etc.)	To protect the assets and company network from malware	Highly critical
		PR2	SBG	Update your antivirus software frequently and ensure you turn on automatic software update.	This will ensure antivirus signature is up to date to provide protection against latest viruses and other malware	Highly critical
		PR3	SBG	Mandate personnel to download applications and software from only approved stores (e.g., Google play store, Apple store, Microsoft apps etc.)	To prevent downloading malicious apps or software from unverified links and stores.	Medium
		PR4	SBG	Track updates and keep all your IT equipment up to date through version	It helps keep computers and network secure and ensure they are functionally reliable.	Highly critical

			upgrade and patching			
		PR5	SBG	Create a password policy that defines set of rules on creating strong password and requires password protection is turned on all relevant account and IT systems. (Laptop, PC, cloud account, smart devices, Hard disk drive, USB etc.)	To ensure policy makes provision for protection of information assets and defines requirements to create strong password	Highly critical
		PR6	SBG	Implement password protection on all relevant account and IT infrastructure (Laptop, PC, Cloud accounts, smart devices, Hard disk drive, USB etc.)	To ensure only authorised personnel can access and use password protected devices	Highly critical
		PR7	SBG	Track updates and keep all your smart and mobile devices up to date through version upgrade installation	It helps keep smart and mobile devices secure and ensure they are functionally reliable.	Highly critical
		PR8	SBG	Configure all smart and mobile devices to enable tracking, remote locking, remote erasure of data stored in case they are stolen or get lost	To ensure ease of retrieval of data for recovery To ensure protection of data through deletion	Critical
		PR9	SBG	Create access control policy and process and spell out requirements for users to be granted access on need basis only.	Policy will spell out requirements for users to be granted only access required to perform their functions	Highly critical
		PR10	SBG	Grant access to users on least privilege basis	To ensure users are granted only privileges which is essential to perform their functions	Highly critical
		PR11	SBG	Configure 2FA for important website and user account	To offer improved security to accessing critical website and user account	Critical

			where the option is available			
		PR12	SBG	Use password manager to manage passwords	To safely store online credentials To generate strong and unique passwords To help employees/users log in into any account automatically	Critical
		PR13	SBG	Change all default passwords on devices and accounts before distributing to staff	To prevent malicious users using publicly available credentials to access or log into devices	Highly critical
		PR14	SBG	Configure automatic email scanning for every email message	To automatically scan every email for viruses, malware, and spam.	Highly critical
		PR15	SBG	Set up encryption on all critical information assets including: - encryption on office equipment (e.g., Bitlocker for windows, FileVault for mac OS etc.) - encryption on storage media (e.g., USB, SD card, HDD etc.) - encryption on network devices (e.g., using WPA2 for Wi-Fi) - encryption on website (i.e. use TLS to encrypt normal HTTP requests and responses, and to digitally sign requests and responses)	To ensure the privacy of digital data that is stored on computer systems, media devices or sent over networks, including the internet.	Highly critical
		PR16	SBG	Create a cybersecurity training plan for all staff on cybersecurity threats, prevention, and reporting. This must be performed annually	To ensure that employees are aware of their potential contribution to strengthening and enforcing the security of the organisation	Highly critical

				or whenever there is a major update.		
		PR17	SBG	Disable physical ports on desktop and laptops for users unless formally approved on need basis	To prevent unauthorised access to the computer's data or prevent the spread of malware through external media devices.	Critical
		PR18	SBG	Configure automatic antivirus scan for connected media storage devices (i.e., USB, HDD, SD cards etc.)	To protect the assets and company network from malware	Highly critical
		PR19	NIST	Enable web filtering to prevent users from accessing unsuitable web content, including malware	To enhance productivity and safeguard the corporate network from web-based risks such as malware, social engineering etc.	Medium
		PR20	NIST	Install and configure software firewall for all your computer systems (laptop, PC, smart devices etc.)	To allow non-threatening traffic in and to keep dangerous traffic out	Highly critical
		PR21	NIST	Mandate staff to use VPN when logged on to unknown networks	To provide a secure and reliable private connection and communication between computer networks	Highly critical
		PR22	NIST	Securely dispose old computers and storage media by wiping sensitive data on the devices	To ensure data has been securely destroyed	Critical
3	Detect	DE1	SBG	Configure automatic scan and perform frequent antivirus scans on all IT device	To protect the assets and company network from malware	Highly critical
		DE2	NIST	Maintain and review logs from antivirus and firewall	To search for anomalies, errors or suspicious activities that can affect security of functional operation of IT devices	Medium
4	Respond	RS1	NIST	Create an incident response plan for different cyberattack scenarios that could	To ensure a formal structure is in place to identify an attack, contain the damage, and eradicate	Highly critical

				threaten data security	the root cause of the incident.	
		RS2	NIST	Put a process in place for employees to report security incidents affecting information assets.	To ensure quick identification and activation of response plan to resolve incident	Critical
5	Recover	RC1	SBG	Create a data backup policy for critical data	To establish a dependable and uniform way of restoring data in case of a disruption.	Highly critical
		RC2	SBG	Create a register for data to be backed up and specify the frequency based on defined recovery point objective (RPO).	To enforce and monitor timely backup of data in line with approved schedule	Critical
		RC3	SBG	Take data backup of critical data	To prevent data loss and guarantee data recovery in the event of business disruption	Highly critical
		RC4	SBG	Review security measures put in place by cloud providers to protect business data in the cloud.	To ensure cloud provider put adequate measures in place to ensure confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information	Critical
		RC5	SBG	Access to data back up (both in cloud and locally) should be restricted	To ensure that only authorised individuals can access information and that the information remains secure and confidential.	Highly critical
		RC6	SBG	Perform frequent review on data backup register	To ensure data backup is performed in a timely, consistent, and adequate manner to meet the recovery point objective (RPO)	Highly critical
		RC7	SBG	Perform frequent review of data backup storage capacity	To ensure data backup capacity and resources are maintained to meet current and future business requirements in a cost-effective manner	Highly critical

Table 4. 1 Hybrid cybersecurity framework functional requirements

Figure 4. 1 Hybrid cybersecurity framework categories

Table 4.1 captures the hybrid cybersecurity framework’s functional requirements designed to provide comprehensive guidance and best practices for small businesses in Nigeria, with a focus on addressing the specific challenges faced by SMEs in the country. Figure 4.1 shows the percentage breakdown of requirements under the 5 categories while Figure 4.2 shows the make-up of the hybrid framework requirement based on the framework’s requirements were sourced from.

Figure 4. 2 Hybrid cybersecurity framework source framework breakdown

The framework requirement specifications will also aim to be user-friendly and practical, with explicit instructions and feasible steps for small business owners and IT teams to implement.

4.3 Implementation of hybrid cybersecurity framework

The implementation of the hybrid cybersecurity framework involved the following steps:

Step 1: Risk assessment and Gaps analysis

The first step in implementation of hybrid framework was a review and audit of existing cybersecurity strategy of small business in Nigeria. This involves using the developed requirements in the customized hybrid cybersecurity framework to assess the adequacy of current framework(s) implemented and existing security controls and tools in place and use the framework as a baseline to review of provisions in organisation's policies and procedures and assess the current level of cybersecurity awareness to identify any gaps in their current cybersecurity posture.

Step 2: Recommendation

Based on the identified gaps, recommendations were provided to address deficiencies in existing practice using the requirements in the hybrid framework. The recommendations details specific actions, methods, leverage policy templates, and free security tools that small businesses can adopt to enhance their cybersecurity posture and protect data to meet the NDPR requirements.

Step 3: Implementation Planning

After recommendation, an implementation plan was developed in consultation with the small business owner, considered timelines (implementation timeline was also agreed during kick-off meeting and captured in the minutes – Appendix C), resources requirements and responsibilities to ensure that it is realistic and achievable whilst I provided support and guidance when required.

Step 4: Implementation

The next step was implementation of the recommendations that were based on the customised hybrid framework. This involved implementing the guidelines and controls specified in the hybrid framework's requirement.

Step 5: Implementation evaluation

Due to limited time for research, hence research subjects commenced implementation, I obtained feedback from the research subjects on how impactful the framework and recommendations were. This was performed using a mix of interview and questionnaire with the small business owners. The aim of the feedback was to help evaluate the effectiveness, usability, and satisfaction of the hybrid framework and recommendations for small businesses in meeting data protection obligation as mandated by the NDPR. The feedback will also help to identify the challenges, areas for improvements from using the framework and highlight areas requiring for further research.

5.0 FINDINGS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings of the research on cybersecurity practices for small businesses in Nigeria to comply with the NDPR data protection requirements. The research adopted a case study approach to examine the experience of 4 small businesses in Nigeria.

The data collection methods used for this research were semi-structured interviews with the business owners and staff of the business, a review of the policy document that outlines the data protection and information security measures of the small business, and a gap analysis questionnaire that was created to measure the alignment of the existing cybersecurity practices with the hybrid cybersecurity framework as a standard for assessment. The case study aims to explore the challenges, opportunities, and best practices of the company in implementing and maintaining a robust cybersecurity program.

5.2 Analysis and findings from case studies

This section presents result from the analysis of the case studies, see Appendix D for full report. The case studies involved four small businesses that were assessed for their level of compliance using the hybrid cybersecurity framework requirement as the target level of maturity for the businesses to achieve information security and data protection objectives. The findings are organized into five subsections. The first four subsections show the individual results of the gap analysis of the compliance level for each of the businesses under the five different categories: Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, and Recover, while the fifth subsection presents result of the overall level of compliance for research subjects and a summary of the common themes and patterns that emerged from the findings across the four case studies.

Category	Count	Target level of compliance	Company A level	Company B level	Company C level	Company D level
Identify	7	26	9	2	2	1
Protect	22	78	14	13	17	20
Detect	2	6	2	1	3	2
Respond	2	7	0	0	2	0
Recover	7	26	4	2	6	4
Grand total	40	143	29	18	30	27

Table 5. 1 Result of gap analysis result showing level of compliance

Table 5.1 shows the result of gap analysis of level of compliance to the hybrid framework as a baseline for complying with data protection regulation. The table shows the target compliance level and the actual compliance score for the four small businesses in the study assessed under five categories of the hybrid framework: Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond and Recover.

Interpretation of the result addresses the research question by specifying how the findings contribute to the understanding of the challenges, opportunities, and current cybersecurity practices of small businesses in Nigeria and will provide a basis for recommendation to address identified gaps.

BOI company category	Company name	Industry	Business type	Number of employees	Total asset value (₦)	Annual Turnover (₦)
Small sized business	A	Law	Legal practice	16	15,000,000	86,600,000
	B	ICT	Information Technology	16	130,000,000	80,000,000
Micro sized business	C	Education	Non-governmental organisation	2	201,000	1,000,000
	D	Law	Corporate services	2	2,000,000	10,000,000

Table 5. 2 Demography of sample research subjects

The demographics of sample are shown in Table 5.2, it shows research subjects are evenly distributed as 2 small sized businesses and 2 micro sized businesses; this was categorized based on the definition by Bank of Industry (n.d.).

5.2.1 Case study – Company A result presentation

Company A is a legal practice that operates in the law industry in Nigeria. The practice has 16 employees and an annual turnover of 86.6 million naira. Company A is categorized as small business in Table 5.2

Figure 5. 1 Target level and Company A compliance level for each category of the hybrid framework

Result of comparative analysis of the company A's level of compliance with the target level is presented in Figure 5.1, the level of compliance under the different category is significantly lower than

the target level under all categories achieving highest level of compliance under “identify” category with 34.6% (9/26) of the target level and the lowest level of compliance under “respond” category with 0% (0/7) due to lack of response plan and process, and the company has a gross percentage score of 20.3% (29/143) indicating that the company has a low level of cybersecurity maturity and needs to improve its cybersecurity practices and capabilities.

5.2.2 Case study – Company B result presentation

Company B is an information technology company that operates in the ICT industry in Nigeria. The practice has 16 employees and an annual turnover of 80 million naira. Company B is categorized as small business in Table 5.2

Figure 5. 2 Target level and Company B compliance level for each category of the hybrid framework

Result of comparative analysis of the company B’s level of compliance with the target level is presented in Figure 5.2, the level of compliance under the different category is significantly lower than the target level under all categories achieving highest level of compliance under both “protect and detect” categories with 16.7% (13/78 and 1/6 respectively) of the target level and the lowest level of compliance under “respond” category with 0% (0/7) due to lack of response plan and process, and the company has a gross percentage score of 12.6% (18/143) indicating that the company has a low level of cybersecurity maturity and needs to improve its cybersecurity practices and capabilities.

5.2.3 Case study – Company C result presentation

Company C is a non-governmental organisation that operates within the Education sector in Nigeria. The organisation has 2 employees and an annual turnover of 1 million naira. Company C is categorized as micro sized business in Table 5.2

Figure 5. 3 Target level and Company C compliance level for each category of the hybrid framework

Result of comparative analysis of the company C's level of compliance with the target level is presented in Figure 5.3, the level of compliance under the different category is significantly lower than the target level under all categories achieving highest level of compliance under "detect" category with 50% (3/6) of the target level and the lowest level of compliance under "identify" category with 7.7% (2/26) due lack of formal information security policy and weak asset management process, and the company has a gross percentage score of 21% (30/143) indicating that the company has a low level of cybersecurity maturity and needs to improve its cybersecurity practices and capabilities.

5.2.4 Case study – Company D result presentation

Company D is a professional services organisation involved in corporate services that operates within the Law industry in Nigeria. The organisation has 2 employees and an annual turnover of 10 million naira. Company D is categorized as micro sized business in Table 5.2

Figure 5. 4 Target level and Company D compliance level for each category of the hybrid framework

Result of comparative analysis of the company D’s level of compliance with the target level is presented in Figure 5.4, the level of compliance under the different category is significantly lower than the target level under all categories achieving highest level of compliance under “detect” category with 33.3% (2/6) of the target level and the lowest level of compliance under “respond” category with 0% (0/7) due to lack of response plan and process, and the company has a gross percentage score of 19% (27/143) indicating that the company has a low level of cybersecurity maturity and needs to improve its cybersecurity practices and capabilities.

5.2.5 Case study findings summary

The summary result of findings revealed cybersecurity practice by small businesses in Nigeria is still at an infant stage. Figure 5.5 illustrates that none of the companies have achieved more than a quarter (25%) of the target compliance weight overall and were not strong enough to defend against or recover from cyber-attacks. It also demonstrates that all the businesses have significant level of cybersecurity activities to perform to achieve a matured cybersecurity posture that will guarantee information security and provide data protection in accordance with the NDPR mandate.

Figure 5. 5 Overall gap analysis report on level of compliance

The following were the recurring themes found in the research:

- The businesses are unaware of the existence of cybersecurity frameworks that could help them enhance their security posture and lower their risks. This is shown by their informal approach to cybersecurity, which lacks a standardized mechanism for developing and maintaining a cybersecurity strategy through adopting a cybersecurity framework.
- Cybersecurity is not given enough consideration during development of business strategy, as many businesses cite lack of budget as a major concern for investing in security measures and solutions.
- Lack of Cybersecurity awareness training and NDPR awareness training for employees which increases their vulnerability to cyberattacks and data breaches.
- There is a lack of skilled cybersecurity professional to lead and manage cybersecurity activities within the businesses.
- The small businesses are leveraging cloud technology for data storage, but they have weak security practices in-house to complement cloud security such as failure to have a formal incident response plan and procedures, failure to update their software and hardware regularly, and lack of cybersecurity awareness training.

The analysis suggests that all research subjects (i.e., company A, B, C & D) need to improve their respective cybersecurity program across all categories to meet the target compliance level and reduce vulnerability to cyber threats. They should adopt a more proactive and comprehensive approach to comply with the regulations and protect their systems and data from cyber threats.

5.3 Overview of outcomes based on research questions

This section presents a summary of the findings to the research question that guided this study. The findings as captured in Table 5.3 are based on the data collected and analysed from the literature review, the gap analysis using the hybrid framework and interviews with business owners.

Question	Answer
RQ1	<p>The existing practices by small businesses in Nigeria to protect data and information assets includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use access control mechanism to manage and grant access to users after authorization. • Use of security tools such as antivirus software, password protection on devices and accounts, and encryption. • Use of cloud technology for data collection and storage and in the process leverage security controls implemented by the cloud provider to secure both data in transit and stored data.
RQ2	<p>The major limitation to the existing practice by small businesses which will make them vulnerable to cyberattacks includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small business owners do not plan, budget, or allocate resources for cybersecurity during their business strategy plan, because they think they are too small to be attacked and there is lack of oversight and enforcement from regulatory bodies due to their small operating scale. • Lack of awareness and adoption of cybersecurity frameworks and formalization of policies and procedures to drive cybersecurity program. For example, they do not have an incident response plan in place, and they do not manage their patching and configuration properly. • Lack of cybersecurity awareness training for staff and relevant third-party contractors on cybersecurity threats detection, prevention, and reporting mechanisms. • Businesses have not familiarized themselves with using other security tools such as firewall to protect their network, password manager, VPN etc. • The businesses do not include personal devices in their cybersecurity strategy, despite using BYOD (Bring Your Own Device) model.
RQ3	<p>The literature review and analysis revealed that some of the existing frameworks available for small businesses in Nigeria to protect data are NCSC Cybersecurity Small Business Guide, NCSC Cyber Essentials and NIST Small Business Information Security. These are good frameworks that could be adopted. They are simple and worded in non-technical terminologies that are easy to understand. They provide guidance and best practices for small businesses to protect data and secure information systems in compliance with the NDPR.</p> <p>Other relevant frameworks that could be adopted are ISO 27001, NIST Cybersecurity Framework and COBIT.</p>

RQ4	<p>These factors hinder the effective adoption and implementation of cybersecurity frameworks for small business in Nigeria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of awareness and sensitization on existing cybersecurity frameworks options, evident in the result of our analysis which shows none of the research subject adopting cybersecurity framework. • Lack of experienced cybersecurity professional with enough skill to understand and implement requirements of the frameworks in maintaining cybersecurity posture for the small businesses in Nigeria. • Lack of cost-effective tools to automate control requirements in the cybersecurity framework. • Lack of budgeting and plan for cybersecurity by small businesses during business strategy, this led to eventual lack of financial and technical resources committed to building and maintaining cybersecurity program. • Overreliance on vendor (such as cloud vendors) to provide security for their information, forgetting the need to invest in securing data and information systems managed locally. • Lack of enforcement by regulator (i.e., NDPB or NITDA), this is due to most small businesses in the country not meeting the data protection audit reporting requirement threshold, reporting applies to business that have processed 1000 personal data within 6 months or 2000 personal data annually and none of the research subject met this threshold as at the time of study.
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Table 5. 3 summary of the findings to the research questions

6.0 CONCLUSIONS

6.1 Evaluation of implementation of the hybrid framework

The purpose of the feedback evaluation is to assess the effectiveness and satisfaction of the research subjects who participated in the project to implement the hybrid cybersecurity framework. The feedback is based on the data collected from questionnaire (Appendix E) that was administered to the research subjects after commencement of implementation to evaluate the quality of the framework, ease of understanding requirements and impact of framework on their respective cybersecurity posture and data protection requirement.

The feedback evaluation reveals the following results:

- The research subjects rated the hybrid framework recommendation on average 4 out of 5 on how good it was able to build cybersecurity posture.
- Most of the research subjects (75%) found the hybrid framework easy to understand, while some (25%) found it somewhat difficult to understand.
- Half of the research subjects (50%) believed to a reasonable extent that the hybrid framework would help them achieve data protection objectives of the NDPR, while the other half (50%) were unsure about it. This implies that some research subjects were confident about the compliance benefits of the framework, while others were uncertain about potential impact of achieving data protection objective using the framework.
- All research subjects said that the hybrid framework provided new insights to them, as it was their first time using a cybersecurity framework to design and maintain their cybersecurity strategy.
- Most of the research subjects (75%) have implemented and attested to helping improve their cybersecurity posture, while one (25%) has not implemented yet due to some constraints or delays.
- Some aspects of the hybrid framework or recommendation were difficult to understand, as these were new terminologies such as encryption, firewall, etc. that the research subjects were not used to.
- The research subjects gave an average rating of 3.5 out of 5 on the ease of implementation of security tools recommended by the hybrid framework.
- All research subjects (100%) said they would recommend the hybrid framework to others within their respective industry.

The feedback evaluation also identifies some areas of improvement or challenge for the hybrid framework implementation, such as:

- a. Providing more clarity and guidance on some cybersecurity concepts or terms
- b. Addressing some barriers or constraints in implementing some security tools
- c. Increasing the confidence and certainty of the research subjects on the compliance benefits of the hybrid framework.

These areas can be addressed by providing more training, support and resources to the research subjects and potential users of the hybrid framework in the future.

6.2 Limitations

To address the project limitation, alternative methods, and strategies to prevent them in the future projects should be presented (Wordvice 2021). This project had several limitations that affected its generalizability, feasibility, and effectiveness. These limitations were:

- No monitoring and post-implementation review due to short timeline and partial implementation of recommendations.
- No benchmark review of hybrid framework with ISO 27001, an international standard for information security management to assess the alignment, gaps, and improvement areas of the hybrid framework with the international standard for information security management.
- Generalization issues due to small sample size, furthermore sample population only included micro and small businesses, as I was unable to recruit any medium-sized enterprises for the research.
- Owing to time constraint for the research, I could not validate the questionnaire used to perform hybrid cybersecurity gap analysis to ensure effectiveness of intended purpose.
- Design of hybrid framework was limited to using only three existing frameworks (NCSC SBG, NCSC CE & NIST SBIS). This was done due to simplicity, popularity, wide acceptability, and ease of customization for small businesses. However, there are other equally important frameworks such as ISO 27001, CIS Control, COBIT etc. that could also be relevant and useful for developing a comprehensive and robust hybrid framework.
- No feedback on role and importance of government and regulatory agencies in promoting and enforcing cybersecurity best practices for small businesses in Nigeria.

To overcome these limitations in the future, the project should:

- a. Allocate more time and resources for project execution and evaluation phases and ensure full implementation and testing of all recommendations.
- b. Conduct comparative analysis of hybrid framework with ISO 27001 and other relevant standards, and identify alignment, gaps, and improvement areas of hybrid framework.
- c. Expand sample size and scope to include medium-sized enterprises and use stratified sampling techniques to ensure balanced representation of different types of businesses.
- d. It would be advantageous to employ validation techniques such as content validity, face validity, pilot testing, reliability testing and construct validity to establish the questionnaire's validity and reliability.
- e. Review and incorporate other frameworks that may offer additional benefits or insights for improving hybrid framework design and implementation.
- f. Conduct interviews or surveys with relevant government agencies and regulatory officials, as well as small business owners or managers, to understand their perspectives and challenges regarding cybersecurity best practices for small businesses.

6.3 Recommendations

This dissertation has explored the challenges and opportunities of cybersecurity for small businesses in Nigeria. Based on the findings and analysis, the following recommendations were proposed:

- Small businesses should adopt a cybersecurity framework (such as NCSC Cybersecurity small business guide, Cyber Essentials, NIST Small Business Information Security, Hybrid cybersecurity framework etc.) that suits their needs and context and use it to develop their cybersecurity strategy. This should be used to formalise policies and processes to ensure proper implementation and maintenance of cybersecurity activities.
- Small businesses should view cybersecurity as a facilitator of their business goals and include it in their business strategy sessions. They should also allocate resources for implementation and maintenance of cybersecurity measures, considering the potential costs and benefits of doing so.
- Small businesses should conduct cybersecurity awareness training for their employees and relevant third-party contractors, to raise their knowledge and skills on cyber threats and best practices, and to foster a culture of responsibility and vigilance.
- Small businesses should spend more time learning about security technologies (e.g., VPN, password manager etc.) and actively look for affordable security tools that can enhance their security posture. For instance, they can visit the SMEDAN (Small & Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria) page that has links to GCA toolkit that provides links to free tools and policy templates and security blogs from vendors and reputable sources that can help them.
- Government and government agencies such as Nigeria Data Protection Bureau (NDPB), National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) should increase their efforts to educate small businesses on the importance and requirements of cybersecurity and provide support for small businesses to adopt cybersecurity measures. This will help achieve a high level of cybersecurity by small businesses. This will be in line with practicable and successful strategy by advance economies using agencies like the National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC) in the UK, European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) for the EU and Cybersecurity & Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) in the US.
- Small businesses should expand the coverage of their IT infrastructure in their cybersecurity strategy implementation to include any system or personal device that can access their network or company's data and apply appropriate security controls to them.

6.4 Improvements and further research work

This study revealed some unexpected findings that could be explored further in future research to enrich and expand the knowledge base on cybersecurity practices in Nigeria and other developing countries. These include:

- The feasibility and effectiveness of using free security tools to implement cybersecurity framework requirements for small businesses, as well as the availability and affordability of other security tools that could offer more benefits or features. This is particularly important in addressing budget constraint cited by research subject.
- The role and impact of regulatory bodies and agencies in Nigeria in raising cybersecurity awareness and enforcing compliance with cybersecurity best practices among small

businesses, which are a vital part of the country's economy. This will create awareness of cybersecurity practices and frameworks to enable businesses proactively adopt a suitable cybersecurity strategy to protect their information assets and comply with data protection regulations.

- The potential and challenges of using cloud technology as a strategy to store and protect data for small businesses in Nigeria, considering the infrastructure, cost, and security issues involved.
- The empirical evaluation of the developed hybrid framework after its full implementation and testing, to assess its performance and outcomes in enhancing the cybersecurity posture and fulfilling the data protection requirements of the NDPR for small businesses.

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APPENDIXES

Appendix A – Glossary

Below is alphabetical listing of terms for this research using ISO 27000:

Access control: means to ensure that access to assets is authorised and restricted based on business and security.

Attack: attempt to destroy, expose, alter, disable, steal or gain unauthorised access to or make unauthorised use of an asset.

Information security: preservation of confidentiality, integrity and availability of information

Information system: set of applications, services, information technology assets, or other information-handling components.

Policy: intentions and direction of an organisation, as formally expressed by its top management.

Process: set of interrelated or interacting activities which transforms inputs into outputs

Requirement: need or expectation that is stated, generally implied or obligatory

Review: activity undertaken to determine the suitability, adequacy, and effectiveness of the subject matter to achieve established objectives.

Threat: potential cause of an unwanted incident, which can result in harm to a system or organisation.

Vulnerability: weakness of an asset or control that can be exploited by one or more threats

Appendix B – Project plan and implementation

In this project, I followed a structured approach to plan, track and execute the tasks. I allocated time for each task and followed the dependencies as documented in the plan (Figure B.1).

S/n	Task	Planned duration	Start date	Target completion date	Completion date	Status
1	Introduction	2 days	18-Jan-23	20-Feb-23	22-Feb-23	Delayed completion
2	Literature Review	2.5 weeks	18-Jan-23	06-Feb-23	22-Feb-23	Delayed completion
3	Project Specification - Methodology	3 days	23-Feb-23	27-Feb-23	06-Mar-23	Delayed completion
4	Project specification - LESP Issues & Project risk	4 days	23-Feb-23	28-Feb-23	12-Apr-23	Delayed completion
5	Design of hybrid cybersecurity framework	4 days	03-Mar-23	08-Mar-23	08-Mar-23	Timely completion
6	Gap assessment and recommendations	10 days	07-Mar-23	17-Mar-23	20-Mar-23	Delayed completion
7	Implementation of hybrid cybersecurity framework	15 days	22-Mar-23	11-Apr-23	On going	Ongoing
8	Findings	7 days	12-Apr-23	20-Apr-23	19-Apr-23	Timely completion
9	Conclusion	7 days	12-Apr-23	20-Apr-23	19-Apr-23	Timely completion

Figure B. 1 Project plan and status

Some tasks were delayed due to unforeseen circumstances such as meeting with the project coordinator, overlapping deliverables, and unrealistic estimates. However, I used the project plan to prioritize and manage the tasks to meet the overall deadline. I also adjusted the start time for some tasks as needed.

In other to cater for time management risk in the project, I had to work with a flexible schedule. Specifically, I worked on weekends and on short notices for the interview and other correspondence with the small businesses to achieve success.

I completed all the tasks except for the full implementation of the hybrid cybersecurity framework. This was due to the significant amount of work required after identifying the gaps from the analysis. I am still working on this task with research subjects during the time of report submission as a personal commitment and professional courtesy.

Appendix C - Research subject recruitment and project plan approach discussions

To recruit small businesses in Nigeria for the project, I shared a WhatsApp message in different groups and invited interested participants to sign up. I then emailed them (Figure C.1) with more details about the project, including the expectations, deliverables and timeline, and asked for their formal consent to participate. Out of the businesses that responded, four agreed to join the project.

Figure C. 1 Mail to recruit participant

I scheduled a follow-up meeting with them (Figure C.2) to discuss the project objectives, plans and timelines, and to get their commitment. After the meeting, I documented and shared the minutes (Figure C.3) with the key deliverables and agreed timelines with the research subjects.

Re: Request for Participation in Evaluation of Cybersecurity Strategy to Protect Data f...

OLAOLUWA OGUNYEMI (2120077)

☺ Reply Reply All Forward 📧 ⋮

Fri 17/02/2023 20:30

Thank you [REDACTED]

Trust your day went well?

I would like to have a short meeting with you on the project plan to discuss matters around the following phases and timelines:

- Requirements gathering
- Gap assessment using relevant Cybersecurity Framework template
- Provide recommendations to address identified gap
- How I will work with yourself and your team to implement the recommendation
- Performance of post implementation review

Please advise a suitable time so I can schedule meeting

Regards

Olaoluwa Ogunyemi

Figure C. 2 Mail to request for meeting

Re: Request for Participation in Evaluation of Cybersecurity Strategy to Protect Data f...

OLAOLUWA OGUNYEMI (2120077)

☺ Reply Reply All Forward 📧 ⋮

Wed 22/02/2023 14:16

Hello [REDACTED]

Thanks for your audience

Key discussion points

Scope of my engagement will include:

- Perform a review/assessment of existing cybersecurity policy, procedure and practices to identify gaps
- Propose recommendations to address gaps...Policy, Process and Tools where applicable

Before audit

- NDA
- Online Drive/ Cloud where requirements would be updated

Timeline

- Assessment - 1 week
- Recommendation and implementation - 1 week
- Post implementation review - 1 week

Regards

Olaoluwa Ogunyemi

Figure C. 3 Mail showing minutes of meeting with research subject

Appendix D - Gap analysis questionnaire and recommended security tools

To conduct the gap analysis, I converted the 40 requirements in the hybrid cybersecurity framework into 51 interview questions in a document titled “**Questionnaire**” which was uploaded to the online drive of research subjects, where they provided their responses. I was able to also track their responses, review and provide recommendations on the document on the business’s respective online drive. Table D.1 shows the hybrid cybersecurity-based questionnaire used to perform the gap analysis.

S/n	Category	Ref ID	CSF	Requirements	Criticality	Response
1	Identify	ID1	NIST	Do you have an information security policy	Highly Critical	Compliant
		ID2	NIST	Do your employees read and consent to requirements of the business' information security policy	Highly Critical	Partly Compliant
		ID3	NIST	Do you have inventory of all your asset	Highly Critical	Not Compliant
			SBG	Do you have an inventory of all your assets with relevant specifications including asset name, operating systems, versions etc.		Compliant
		ID4	NIST	Do you test employees understanding of the information security policy annually or when there is a major change to the policy	Highly Critical	Partly Compliant
		ID5	NIST	Do you obtain employee's consent to the requirements in the information security policy If yes, do you file the consent in their respective HR files	Highly Critical	Not Compliant
		ID6	SBG AP	Do you have any dedicated staff signed up to threat alerts and newsletters to monitor emerging cybersecurity threats If yes, are the threat trends communicated to employees and used to develop user awareness training resources	Critical	Compliant
		ID7	SBG AP	Do you have an inventory of approved storage media If yes, do you review the	Critical	Partly Compliant

				inventory and their issued owners		
2	Protect	PR1	SBG	Do you have anti-virus installed on all devices	Highly Critical	Not Compliant
		PR2	SBG	Do you update your antivirus frequently If yes, are antivirus software updates automatic or manually applied	Highly Critical	Compliant
		PR3	SBG	Are staff mandated to download applications and software from only approved stores (e.g., Google Play, Apple store, Microsoft apps etc.)	Medium	Partly Compliant
		PR4	SBG	Do you track updates and keep all your IT equipment up to date through version upgrade and patching If yes, please specify the frequency of monitoring (Monthly, Quarterly, etc.)	Highly Critical	Not Compliant
		PR5	SBG	Do you have a password policy that requires password protection is turned on all relevant IT systems. (Laptop, PC, cloud account, smart devices, Hard disk drive, USB etc.) If yes, please specify how it is enforced	Highly Critical	Compliant
			SBG	Does the password policy define minimum length, mandatory mix of alphabets, numbers and special characters. Is this enforced? If yes, specify how		Partly Compliant
		PR6	SBG	Do you have password protection turned on all relevant IT infrastructure	Highly Critical	Not Compliant
			SBG	Are all smart devices that can access the businesses data		Compliant

			password protected (use a mix or either of PIN, password or biometric)			
		PR7	SBG	Do you keep operating systems and applications on smart devices up to date. (Please indicate if automatic update is configured for the operating systems and apps)	Highly Critical	Partly Compliant
		PR8	SBG	Are all smart devices configured to enable tracking, remote locking, remote erasure of data store in case they are stolen or get lost	Critical	Not Compliant
		PR9	SBG AP	Do you have a defined access control for users to ensure access is granted on need basis only. Please provide comment on how it is being enforced	Highly Critical	Compliant
		PR10	SBG	Are access administration profile configuration for user on least privilege basis	Highly Critical	Partly Compliant
		PR11	SBG	Do you use 2 factor authentication for important website and to protect critical data where the option is available (e.g., email, bank account etc.)	Critical	Not Compliant
		PR12	SBG	Do staff use password manager to manage passwords	Critical	Compliant
		PR13	SBG	Do you change all default passwords on devices and accounts before distributing to staff	Highly Critical	Partly Compliant
		PR14	SBG	Are emails configured to scan malicious links and attachments	Highly Critical	Not Compliant
	NIST		Did you turn on email filter options	Compliant		
		PR15	SBG TA	Did you set up encryption on all office equipment (e.g., Bitlocker for windows, FileVault for mac OS) and website	Highly Critical	Partly Compliant
			NIST	Did you change the default admin password on your router		Not Compliant

			NIST	Did you set your router to use Wi-Fi protected access 2 (WPA 2) with advanced encryption standard (AES)		Compliant
			NIST	Do you encrypt your storage media devices (Hard Drive, USB, SD cards etc.)		Partly Compliant
			NIST	Do you collect sensitive business information online through using encrypted communication - (HTTPS still active on the URL)		Not Compliant
		PR16	SBG TA	Do you have a cybersecurity training plan for all staff on cybersecurity threats, prevention and reporting If yes, what is the frequency	Highly Critical	Compliant
		PR17	SBG	Are physical ports on desktop and laptops blocked for users unless formally approved on need basis	Critical	Partly Compliant
		PR18	SBG	Do you use antivirus tools to always scan connected media storage devices such as USB, Hard disk drive, SD cards etc.	Highly Critical	Not Compliant
		PR19	NIST	Did you enable web filtering on browsers	Medium	Compliant
		PR20	NIST	Did you install and configure software firewall for all your computer systems (laptop, PC, smart devices etc.)	Highly Critical	Partly Compliant
		PR21	NIST	Do you mandate staff to use VPN when logged on to unknown networks	Highly Critical	Not Compliant
		PR22	NIST	Do you securely dispose of old computers and media by wiping sensitive data on the devices	Critical	Compliant
3	Detect	DE1	SBG	Do you perform antivirus scans frequently	Highly Critical	Partly Compliant
				If yes, are the antivirus scans scheduled automatically or are they scheduled manually		
		DE2	NIST	Do you maintain and monitor logs (antivirus and firewall)	Medium	Not Compliant
NIST	Do you review firewall and antivirus logs monthly		Compliant			
4	Respond	RS1	NIST	Do you have an incident response plan	Highly Critical	Partly Compliant

		RS2	NIST	Do you have a process in place for employees to report incidents	Critical	Not Compliant
5	Recover	RC1	SBG	Do you have a data backup policy	Highly Critical	Compliant
		RC2	SBG	Do you have any asset classification document that specifies data to be backed up If yes, is the backup frequency specified	Critical	Partly Compliant
		RC3	SBG	Do you take data backup locally e.g., Hard disk drives, other media storage device etc.	Highly Critical	Not Compliant
			SBG	What security measures did you put in place to secure data stored locally		Compliant
			SBG	Do you take data backup using cloud If yes, please specify the cloud services being used and the purpose (e.g., emails, host website, storage etc.)		Partly Compliant
		RC4	SBG	What security measures did you consider before adopting cloud services	Critical	Not Compliant
		RC5	SBG	Is access to the data backup restricted If yes, please indicate how	Highly Critical	Compliant
		RC6	SBG	Do you have a backup register that specifies details of data to be backed up and the frequency? If yes, is the register always signed and reviewed after backup is completed	Highly Critical	Partly Compliant
RC7	SBG	Do you review storage capacity for the backup (local and cloud)	Highly Critical	Not Compliant		

Table D. 1 Hybrid framework assessment questionnaire

To perform the gap analysis of compliance for the response, I followed these steps:

- I weighted each functional requirement of the cybersecurity framework according to its importance for data protection and information security. I used a four-point criticality ranking scale: Highly critical = 4; Critical = 3; Medium = 2; Low = 1.
- I rated each functional requirement for each company based on the gap analysis. I used a three-point implementation level tier scale: Compliant = 2; Partly compliant = 1 ; Not compliant = 0.
- I calculated the target level of compliance for each functional requirement by multiplying the weight by 2, which means full compliance with the requirement. This is the expected level of implementation to meet the NDPR data protection requirement using the hybrid cybersecurity framework as the standard.
- I calculated the actual level of compliance for each functional requirement for each company by multiplying the weight by the rating assigned after the gap analysis.

S/n	Category	Ref ID	Criticality ranking	Targeted level of compliance			Company A		Company B		Company C		Company D	
				Criticality weight [A]	Targeted weight [B]	Target LOC [C] = [A]*[B]	IW - A [D]	LOC - A [E] = [A]*[D]	IW - B [F]	LOC - B [G] = [A]*[F]	IW - C [H]	LOC - C [I] = [A]*[H]	IW - D [J]	LOC - D [K] = [A]*[J]
1	Identify	ID1	Highly critical	4	2	8	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
		ID2	Highly critical	4	2	8	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
		ID3	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	4
		ID4	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	0	0	1	4	0	0
		ID5	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
		ID6	Critical	3	2	6	1	3	1	3	0	0	0	0
		ID7	Critical	3	2	6	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Protect	PR1	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	1	4	2	8	2	8
		PR2	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	1	4	2	8	2	8
		PR3	Medium	2	2	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		PR4	Highly critical	4	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	8
		PR5	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	0	0	0	0	1	4
		PR6	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	4
		PR7	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	1	4	1	4	0	0
		PR8	Critical	3	2	6	1	3	1	3	0	0	0	0
		PR9	Highly critical	4	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		PR10	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	1	4	1	4	0	0
		PR11	Critical	3	2	6	1	3	2	6	2	6	0	0
		PR12	Critical	3	2	6	1	3	0	0	2	6	2	6
		PR13	Highly critical	4	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	8
		PR14	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	4
		PR15	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	4
PR16	Highly critical	4	2	8	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	0		
PR17	Critical	3	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
PR18	Highly critical	4	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	8		
PR19	Medium	2	2	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
PR20	Highly critical	4	2	8	0	0	1	4	2	8	2	8		
PR21	Highly critical	4	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
PR22	Medium	2	2	4	2	4	2	4	2	4	2	4		
3	Detect	DE1	Highly critical	4	2	8	2	8	1	4	2	8	2	8
		DE2	Medium	2	2	4	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0
4	Respond	RS1	Highly critical	4	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RS2	Critical	3	2	6	0	0	0	0	2	6	0	0
5	Recover	RC1	Highly critical	4	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RC2	Critical	3	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RC3	Highly critical	4	2	8	2	8	2	8	2	8	2	8
		RC4	Critical	3	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RC5	Highly critical	4	2	8	2	8	0	0	2	8	0	0
		RC6	Highly critical	4	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		RC7	Highly critical	4	2	8	0	0	0	0	2	8	2	8
Grand Total				143	80	286	29	107	18	64	30	108	27	102

Acronyms

LOC	Level of Compliance
IW	Implementation weight

Legends

A

Criticality weight legend

Highly Critical	4
Critical	3
Medium	2
Low	1

B

Implementation level legend

Compliant	2
Partly compliant	1
Not compliant	0

Excel column with formula were colored

	Target Level of Compliance
	Target Level of Compliance

Figure D. 1 Level of compliance analysis schedule

The result of the gap analysis for the respective small business was appraised against the target level of compliance as indicated in Figure D.1*.

The gap analysis revealed that the research subjects had significant level of work to implement recommendations. To help them, I searched for free and open-source security tools, policy templates,

training links, online security control tips by vendors and blogposts that were relevant to their needs. I compiled 44 links in total captured in Figure D.2 used as recommendations for security tools and policies to be leveraged and implemented by research subjects.

S/n	Tools	Purpose	Link
1	GCA toolkit	Free Cybersecurity Tools to Secure Your Organization, including security tools, templates, security guideline links, training links etc	https://gcatoolkit.org/
2	SANS Information Security Policy template	Security Policy templates	https://www.sans.org/information-security-policy/?page=2
3	CIS Hardware and Software asset tracker	Templates to record and track hardware and software inventory	https://www.cisecurity.org/white-papers/cis-hardware-and-software-asset-tracking-spreadsheet/
4	Fing	Network scanner & device blocking app for Internet security	https://www.fing.com
5	NCSC Threat reports	To get update on emerging threat trends and prevention tips	https://www.ncsc.gov.uk/section/keep-up-to-date/threat-reports?q=&defaultTypes=report&sort=date%2Bdesc
6	Microsoft security protection tips	Tips and updates from Microsoft on securing systems configuration to prevent malware	https://support.microsoft.com/en-gb/windows/stay-protected-with-windows-security-2ae0363d-0ada-c064-8b56-6a39afb6a963
7	Apple mobile device update tips	Instructions on how to update apps manually on Apple device	https://support.apple.com/en-gb/HT201541
8	Apple laptop and desktop device update tips	Instructions on how to update macOS on Mac	https://support.apple.com/en-gb/HT201541
9	Microsoft 365 update tips on Mac	Instructions on how to update Microsoft 365 on Mac	https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/update-office-for-mac-automatically-bfd1e497-c24d-4754-92ab-910a074d7c17?ui=en-us&rs=en-gb&ad=gb
10	Microsoft tips on PC update	Instructions on keeping Microsoft PC up to date	https://support.microsoft.com/en-gb/windows/keep-your-pc-up-to-date-de79813c-7919-5fed-080f-0871c7bd9bde
11	Google tips on how to update apps	Instructions on how to update the Play Store & apps on Android	https://support.google.com/googleplay/answer/113412
12	Password characteristics best practice	Guide on how to develop strong passwords	https://specopssoft.com/blog/password-length-best-practices/
13	Have been pwned	Check if password has been compromised	https://haveibeenpwned.com
14	Password auditor	Scan your active directory and detect security weaknesses related to password settings	https://specopssoft.com/product/specops-password-auditor/
15	2FA for online accounts	To request for 2FA on account	https://2fadiirectory/gb/
16	Google authenticator for android	2FA authentication tool for advanced protection of online accounts	https://support.google.com/accounts/answer/1066447?co=GENIE.Platform%3DAndroid
17	Microsoft authenticator	2FA authentication tool for advanced protection of online accounts	https://www.microsoft.com/en-gb/security/mobile-authenticator-app
18	2FA on gmail	How to set up 2FA for gmail	https://safety.google/authentication/
19	2FA for apple	Instruction on setting up 2FA for apple	https://support.apple.com/en-gb/HT204915
20	2FA on whatsapp	Instruction on setting up 2FA on whatsapp	https://faq.whatsapp.com/1920866721452534/?locale=en_US
21	2FA Microsoft 365	Instruction on setting up multifactor authentication for Microsoft 365	https://learn.microsoft.com/en-gb/microsoft-365/admin/security-and-compliance/set-up-multi-factor-authentication?view=0365-worldwide
22	Password manager	Tool to secure password credentials	https://bitwarden.com
23	Email filter settings guide	How to set up rules to detect harmful attachments	https://support.google.com/a/answer/7676854?hl=en
24	Email filter guide	Blogpost on how to Scan to email from Windows 10 with Gmail or any email account	https://support.itsolver.net/hc/en-au/articles/360000494136-How-to-Scan-to-email-from-Windows-10-with-Gmail-or-any-email-account
25	VPN	VPN to secure internet connection to office network	https://protonvpn.com
26	Encrypt media storage device on windows	BitLocker to encrypt Hard drive, USB, SD cards on windows	https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/turn-on-device-encryption-0c453637-bc88-5f74-5105-741561aa838#MDOEBD=Windows_10
27	Encrypt startup disk on Mac	FileVault to encrypt your Mac startup disk	https://support.apple.com/en-us/HT204837
28	Email encryption tool	Encrypt all email	https://www.openpgp.org
29	Encrypt your website	Encrypt your website to secure communications	https://letsencrypt.org/getting-started/
30	Website security testing tool	Scan your website to find security issues	https://www.immunibweb.com/websec/
31	SSL security test	Find encryption weakness in your website	https://www.immunibweb.com/ssl/
32	Change default wifi router password	Instructions on how to change default router password	https://helpcenter.trendmicro.com/en-us/article/tmka-20524
33	Configure wifi router to use WPA	Instruction on how to Configure Your Router to Use WPA2 for better security	https://helpcenter.trendmicro.com/en-us/article/tmka-20644
34	NCSC's cyber security training	NCSC's cyber security training	https://www.ncsc.gov.uk/blog-post/ncsc-cyber-security-training-for-staff-now-available
35	Block site	Block any website you wish to restrict staff access to (blacklist)	https://chrome.google.com/webstore/detail/block-site/lebigkcaodkkmjelmboqdedcpnmbf7h?hl=en
36	Firewall settings configuration on router	Instruction on how to Change Firewall Settings on a Router	https://www.gadgetreview.com/how-to-change-firewall-settings-on-router
37	Secure asset disposal guideline	Guidance for development of secure asset disposal process	https://ico.org.uk/media/for-organisations/documents/1570/it_asset_disposal_for_organisations.pdf
38	Log retention best practices	Blogpost on log retention	https://www.logicmonitor.com/blog/what-is-log-retention
39	Log analysis best practices	Blogpost on important of log analysis	https://thenextscoop.com/log-analysis-business/
40	NCSC Small Business Guide: Response & Recovery	Guidance that helps small to medium sized organisations prepare their response and plan their recovery from a cyber incident.	https://www.ncsc.gov.uk/collection/small-business-guidance-response-and-recovery
41	Cyber hygiene training	Free course on cyber hygiene	https://trailhead.salesforce.com/content/learn/modules/cyber-hygiene
42	Backup and restore tips for Windows	How to Backup and Restore in Windows	https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/backup-and-restore-in-windows-352091d2-bb9d-3ea3-ed18-52ef2b88cbef
43	Backup tips for Mac	Automatic backup configuration on mac	https://support.apple.com/en-gb/HT201250
44	NCSC Cloud Security tips	Cloud security guidance tips on how to choose, deploy and use cloud services securely	https://www.ncsc.gov.uk/collection/cloud/the-cloud-security-principles

Figure D. 2 Links for security tools, security blogs and security policy templates

**Take note of the acronyms and legends on the gap analysis schedule*

Appendix E – Feedback evaluation from research subject

In evaluation of impact and effect of recommendation and hybrid framework implementation, I used the following questionnaire to obtain information from research subjects Figure E.1 and E.2

Part A: General question		
These are general questions to assess your approach to cybersecurity, understanding and consideration of the NDPR requirements in your data protection strategy		
S/n	Question	Answer
1	How much consideration does your organization give to cybersecurity during the development of its business strategy?	
2	How aware is your organization of the need to comply with data protection requirements of the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR)?	
3	Who do you consider to be responsible for the security and protection of data in the cloud? a. Only cloud provider b. Your business and cloud provider	
4	To what extent does your organization provide user awareness training for cybersecurity? a. Not at all b. Rarely c. Sometimes d. Often e. Always	
5	To what extent does your organization provide NDPR awareness training? a. Not at all b. Rarely c. Sometimes d. Often e. Always	
6	What are the major challenges your organization faces when implementing cybersecurity measures? (Select all that applies) a. Lack of budget b. Lack of skilled personnel c. Lack of management support d. Lack of awareness e. Other If Others, please specify	
7	Are you aware of any cybersecurity frameworks that can be used to develop a cybersecurity strategy? If yes, please name the ones you know.	
8	What are the most important security controls implemented to protect your data? (Select all that applies) a. Encryption b. Access controls c. Firewalls d. Intrusion detection and prevention e. Other If others, please specify	
9	Does your organization have an information security policy? a. Yes b. No If yes, were the NDPR requirements considered during its development?	
10	Did you factor in NDPR requirements in your data protection strategy? a. Yes b. No If yes, please indicate how.	

Figure E. 1 General questionnaire to assess approach to cybersecurity

Part B: Hybrid Cybersecurity Framework implementation question		
Background		
Assessment of your existing cybersecurity posture was performed using a customised Hybrid Cybersecurity Framework to identify gaps and it formed the basis for the recommendations.		
The Hybrid Cybersecurity Framework was developed by reviewing the NDPR data protection requirements and fusing 3 different cybersecurity framework (i.e. NCSC Cybersecurity Small Business Guide, NCSC Cyber Essentials and NIST Small Business Information Security) to form a customised framework specifically designed for small business in Nigeria		
S/n	Question	Answer
1	On a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being very poor and 5 being excellent, how would you rate the hybrid cybersecurity framework and recommendations provided to you? 1. Very poor 2. Poor 3. Good 4. Very Good 5. Excellent	
2	Did you find the hybrid cybersecurity framework and recommendations easy to understand? a. Yes b. No	
3	To what extent do you believe the hybrid cybersecurity framework and recommendations have helped you achieve your data protection objectives? a. Completely b. To a large extent c. To some extent d. Not at all	
4	Did the hybrid cybersecurity framework and recommendations provide new insights or perspectives to your cybersecurity strategy? a. Yes b. No	
5	Have you implemented any of the recommendations provided in the hybrid cybersecurity framework? a. Yes b. No If yes, what were the results? a. Significant improvement in cybersecurity posture b. Some improvement in cybersecurity posture c. No improvement in cybersecurity posture	
6	Were there any aspects of the hybrid cybersecurity framework or recommendations that were difficult to implement? a. Yes b. No	
7	Would you recommend the hybrid cybersecurity framework to other businesses in your industry? a. Yes b. No	
8	If you have any additional comments or feedback about your experience with the hybrid cybersecurity framework and recommendations, please share below.	

Figure E. 2 Questionnaire to evaluate feedback on recommendation and hybrid framework implementation